

ACTIVITY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES ON IMPROVING THE LEGAL CULTURE OF THE POPULATION IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE NEW UZBEKISTAN: PROBLEMS AND WAYS TO ELIMINATE THEM

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ABSTRACT

The scientific article compares the scientific-theoretical aspects of raising legal culture in society, the reforms implemented in its modern stage. Also, in recent years, internal affairs bodies have thoroughly analyzed the activities of forming the legal culture of the population and future tasks.

In recent years, systematic reforms have been implemented in our country to improve the legal literacy of the population.

However, when the work in this direction is analyzed, it becomes clear that the development of the legal culture of the society is seen only as the work of the law enforcement agencies, and that the work on improving the legal culture of the population is not systematically carried out by the family, neighborhood, educational institutions, enterprises and organizations, as well as civil society institutions.

In order to eliminate the above problems, a number of tasks have been assigned to the internal affairs bodies, which have their place in raising the legal culture among the population.

In particular, when analyzing the work done by the internal affairs bodies in terms of legal promotion and raising legal culture, during the past period, in cooperation with the justice bodies and public organizations, we have discussed with the population and young people about raising legal culture in the society, "The spirit of respect for laws in the society is the guarantee of building a democratic legal state!" it became known that meetings, conferences, discussions and roundtables are being organized based on the conceptual idea.

In particular, as an important factor in the formation of civil society in the ongoing propaganda activities, the work on increasing the legal literacy of the population is aimed at uniform and correct understanding of the legislation adopted by the state, support for its implementation, prevention of cases of legal nihilism, formation of the spirit of obedience to the laws and, most importantly, the actual opinions are given that it helps to form a feeling of goodwill towards the political authorities.

Of course, in the process of improving the legal culture of the society, there are also influencing factors that hinder the performance of the tasks before the internal affairs bodies.

In particular, in today's complex globalization era, the turbulent situations prevailing in different regions of the world, armed conflicts, organized transnational crime, terrorism and extremism, drug business, corruption, etc. not to fight, but to develop preventive measures that prevent them.

It is a difficult task to convey such measures directly to all layers of the society individually, in the form of legal propaganda, and it encourages the internal affairs bodies to strengthen cooperation with the neighborhood and other institutions of civil society, non-governmental non-profit organizations and the general public.

In this direction, the establishment of a new system of parliamentary and public control over the activities of the internal affairs bodies, the introduction of the practice of reporting to the public from the head of the internal affairs body to the prevention inspector, serves to further increase the trust of the population in them.

The practice of reporting to people's representatives makes it possible to acquaint the population with the criminogenic situation in a certain area, as well as with the legislative documents that are being adopted. Citizens' opinions on this matter will help to study their attitude to the current situation and determine their future activities.

If we pay attention to the analysis of the crimes committed in our republic, the fact that most of them are committed by young people shows that it is necessary to pay the main attention to this layer, which makes up 60% of the population. Forming a spirit of obedience and respect for the law among young people, increasing their legal literacy, promoting their rights and freedoms without forgetting their duties and responsibilities, protecting and preventing information attacks that promote negative evils in the era of fast information remains one of the urgent issues.

Juvenile inspectors of the internal affairs bodies introduced in secondary educational institutions are responsible for the above tasks, and it is necessary to help them organize their work method based on an innovative approach based on scientific research. Time has shown that young people cannot be approached through old-fashioned attendance and other warning measures.

Also, the role of the employees of the internal affairs bodies (especially prevention inspectors) is important in increasing the legal culture of the population and teaching citizens to be able to assess the socio-economic problems that may arise in social life based on the correct analysis. For this, it is necessary for the internal affairs bodies to act as "servants of the people", as the head of state said.

As a result of the conducted research, it can be said that the most effective way to fight against crime is prevention, that is, prevention of offenses. For this purpose, one prevention inspector was assigned to each neighborhood, and they were given the status of deputy chairman of the neighborhood.

With this, the task of the prevention inspector is not to be an inspector or supervisor, but to be a force that helps the residents of the neighborhood in all vital matters, is a legal protector and consultant, and is a force that stands side by side. In order to continuously organize the activities of these employees and bring them closer to the population, service houses were built for them in their territory.

Positions of inspectors for women's issues were introduced, consisting of female employees, working with women's problems in the neighborhood. Today, in cooperation with the deputy chairpersons of the citizens' meetings on women's issues, they are becoming advisers and defenders in increasing the legal literacy of women, and preventing them from becoming victims of oppression and violence.

As the existence of a population with undeveloped legal consciousness and low level of legal literacy is a problem for the state, the increase of this category poses a serious threat to the security of the state and society. This is proven by the events related to the color revolutions and the change of the political system that took place in the territory of foreign countries during recent and past history. In such cases, the maintenance of public order and public safety has a negative impact on the activities of not only internal affairs bodies, but also all law enforcement bodies.

Therefore, the concept of public security, adopted on the basis of the Presidential decree, opened the way to improve the activities of the internal affairs bodies in improving the legal culture of the society, bringing them closer to the people.¹

Also, with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 27, 2019 "On additional measures to ensure the independence of the mass media and the development of the information services of state bodies and organizations", the activities of the Press Service of the internal affairs bodies were also improved.

Through press services, legal information and propaganda work has been widely launched through mass media on social and legal problems that are bothering the population.

It has become customary to show a series of shows and video films under the name "Criminal Truth and Justice".

Also, the announcement of a quick official reaction to the news and content related to the industry released by the press services to the mass media serves to strengthen its preventive effect.

After all, "it is important to raise the legal consciousness and culture of the population, to convey the essence of the adopted laws and decisions to the general public in the establishment of a democratic state and civil society."²

In addition, according to experts in the field, while the level of legal literacy is improving year by year in the process of communication with citizens involved in the investigation, inquiry and preliminary investigation processes, their recognition and implementation of the law-abiding spirit, duties and obligations is still lacking. indicates that a lot of propaganda work should be done.

In such cases, the desire of citizens to put their personal interests above the interests of society and the state can be an obstacle to the transition from a legal democratic state to a free civil society.

¹ Decree No. PF-27 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 29.11.2021 "On approval of the concept of public safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan and measures for its implementation". <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/5749291>. Application date is 30.09.2022

² Mirziyoev Sh.M. From the speech at the joint session of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis entitled "We will firmly continue the path of democratic reforms based on the new development strategy of Uzbekistan" 06.11.2021

It is known that a citizen uses the least amount of legal knowledge in his work, in his daily life and in his family. This knowledge usually concerns constitutional, labor, family, civil, and entrepreneurial rights. The fact that citizens have extensive legal knowledge does not mean a high level of legal culture, because legal culture includes not only legal knowledge, but also the ability to apply it and demonstrate legal activity.³

To the extent that a person is aware of more laws, he can evaluate the possibility of what to do or not to do in any situation, and this person will have a higher sense of obedience to the law than others. The positive influence of this person can be seen in the fact that he shares his legal knowledge with others, stops the person who is ready to do wrong, and gives him legal advice. A person who is aware of his rights will be able to make legal demands if his rights are violated. It forces the authorized body and its officials to work legally.

The main task of every employee of the internal affairs bodies in the process of improving the legal culture of citizens is to explain the reforms implemented by the state to the population.

By improving the legal culture of society, it is possible to create an environment of intolerance towards corrupt actions that threaten the security of the state and society.

The development of the legal culture of the society leads to ensuring the balance between the interests of the individual and the interests of the society, and the interests of the state are realized (for example, the principle of the inevitability of punishment for crime).

The level of legal culture is determined not by the number of laws adopted, but by its full implementation. Even the most mature and thorough law will remain insignificant as a value if it does not find its application in social life. The great French thinker S.L. Montesquieu wrote: "When I go to a country, I am interested not in the presence of good laws, but in how the laws are obeyed, because good laws are everywhere."⁴

Therefore, using the capabilities of internal affairs bodies in raising the legal consciousness and culture of the society, firstly, ensures the rule of law and legal order in the society; secondly, by bringing the law closer to people, obedience to the law and intolerance to the violation of the law is formed; thirdly, it forms legal immunity against factors that have a negative impact on the legal education of young people; fourthly, it increases the value of law; fifth, it increases the legal literacy of the population; sixth, it serves as an effective tool in establishing a democratic-legal state; seventhly, it prevents a nihilistic (disbelief, disdain) attitude towards law.

In conclusion, it can be said that in the activities of the internal affairs bodies to raise the legal consciousness and culture of the society, it is necessary to improve the system of consistently conveying the content and essence of the socio-economic reforms implemented in our country, adopted legal documents and state programs, and in the future its "province-city-district-neighborhood-household" It is necessary to introduce the mechanism.

In improving the system and the implementation mechanism, priority should be given to uniform and clear understanding of the adopted legislation, support for its implementation,

³ Jalilov A., Kadyrov J. and others. Foundations of civil society. Study guide. Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent. 2015, - P.149.

⁴ Montesquieu Sh.L. Izbrannyye proizvedeniya. O zonax, ob ix otnosheniya k razlichnym sushchestvam. - M.: 1955. - P. 164-165.

prevention of cases of legal nihilism, formation of the spirit of obedience to the laws, and the formation of a feeling of benevolence in the citizens towards the current political authority.

In addition, the development of a system of measures to improve the legal consciousness and culture of students of higher and secondary special educational institutions, employees of enterprises, institutions and organizations is becoming a necessity in the activities of internal affairs bodies.

In this case, it would be appropriate to deeply inculcate the concepts of rights and duties, honesty and purity, as well as norms of etiquette, to organize legal-educational activities to increase legal literacy among the population in harmony with teaching the history, religion, and national values of our people.

Also, the lack of interdepartmental normative legal document at the government level, which ensures the involvement of the general public and representatives of interested ministries and departments in the "Crime Prevention Day" events every Thursday of the week in connection with the serious and extremely serious crimes committed by the internal affairs bodies, also affects the effectiveness of the events. has a negative effect.

Based on the above considerations, it is appropriate to implement the following measures:

introduction of the "province-city-district-neighborhood-household" system and development of its mechanisms for consistently conveying the content and essence of the socio-economic reforms, adopted legal documents and state programs in the activities of internal affairs bodies;

in the development of this system and implementation mechanism, to give priority to uniform and clear understanding of the adopted legislation, support for its implementation, prevention of cases of legal nihilism, formation of the spirit of obedience to laws and the formation of a feeling of benevolence in citizens towards the current political power;

developing a program of measures to improve the legal consciousness and culture of students of higher and secondary special educational institutions, employees of enterprises, institutions and organizations in the activities of internal affairs bodies;

adoption of an interdepartmental regulatory legal document or joint decision at the government level, which ensures that the discussion of crimes in connection with committed serious and extremely serious crimes and the involvement of the general public and representatives of interested ministries and agencies in the events of "Crime Prevention Day" every Thursday of the week;

organizing legal challenges in cooperation with internal affairs bodies, law enforcement bodies and state organizations on legal literacy through social networks and mass media;

wide application of new work methods and mechanisms, in particular digital technologies, to the practical activities of internal affairs bodies to improve legal culture, having studied the advanced experience of developed foreign countries in depth.